

Comparison Study between Regulations Implementations in Indonesia and Thailand to Protect Women from Discrimination in the Workplace

Shannia Yesenia, S.H.¹, Dr. Said Rizal, S.H.I., M.A.², Dr. Immanuel Simanjuntak, S.H., M.H.³

¹ Postgraduate Master Student, Faculty of Law, Universitas Prima Indonesia, Medan

^{2,3} Faculty of Law, Universitas Prima Indonesia, Medan

ABSTRACT: Women's rights have become a focal point in a series of international conferences that have resulted in significant political commitments to human rights and gender equality. Women still face many challenges in their daily lives, including in the workplace. This research aims to provide an analysis of the position of working women in Indonesia and Thailand who experience discrimination in the workforce. By comparing a series of legal regulations that each of these countries has, particularly regarding the protection of female labour. Economic growth, which is also supported by the increasing participation of women in the workforce, is a strong reason why protection for women in the workplace must be prioritized by both countries. This research uses a normative legal method, which is a research method that involves investigating literature or secondary materials, namely laws regulated based on the rules contained in legislation or law used as a guide for behaviour in the daily lives of society. To complement the results of the writing, a qualitative approach is also used. The issues to be addressed in this study are the forms of legal regulations that govern female workers in Indonesia and Thailand to prevent discrimination, the role of law in promoting the empowerment of women working in Indonesia and Thailand, and the legal status of victims of discrimination against female workers in Indonesia and Thailand. The results of the research indicate that there are still many shortcomings in both countries in protecting their respective female workers. The role of the regulations provided by both Indonesia and Thailand has its own role in the effort to ensure protection for women in the workforce. Starting from regulations regarding wages, working hours, leave rights, and protection for women experiencing discrimination or harassment in the workplace. These regulations are made with the intention to be implemented in every field of work, both formal and informal, for women working in Indonesia and Thailand. The position of victims of discrimination in the workplace in both Indonesia and Thailand still faces various kinds of very concerning challenges. Despite the existence of a series of regulations specifically for this protection, they still do not receive justice commensurate with the authorities. Women victims of discrimination must continue to fight to ensure that they receive fair justice.

KEYWORDS: Economic growth, Workplace, Women, Indonesia, Thailand

INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, there are various regulations and institutions dedicated to protecting women in the workplace, Indonesia's 1984 ratification Act of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women and the Indonesian Manpower Act of 2003. Women-based institutes, such as the National Commission on Violence Against Women and the Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection, play a role in protecting women in Indonesia. Thailand, meanwhile, has various institutions and foundations, such as the Office of Women's Affairs and Family Development and the Teeranat Kanjanauksorn Foundation, which continue to operate today. This study explains the differences and similarities in the regulatory frameworks for implementing labor law in Indonesia and Thailand, as well as the challenges faced by female workers in both countries. In general, both countries have laws governing employment, such as the Employment Act in Indonesia and the Gender Equality Act 2015 in Thailand.

A. Regulation Comparisons

Thailand has advanced women's rights and gender equality through ratification of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women in 1985 and its Optional Protocol in 2000, support for the Beijing Platform for Action (BPFA) in 1995, and commitment to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015. In general, the Indonesian 2003 labour law explains that every worker has the same rights and opportunities to obtain decent work and livelihood without distinction of sex, ethnicity, race, religion, and political affiliation in accordance with the interests and abilities of the worker concerned, including

equal treatment for people with disabilities and every employer is obliged to provide the rights and obligations of workers/labourers without distinction of sex, ethnicity, race, religion, skin colour, and political affiliation. A brief comparison of the two nation's law regarding their protection for women in the workplace.

<i>Topic</i>	<i>Indonesia</i>	<i>Thailand</i>
Prohibition of night work for women under 18	Act 76 Section 1: Women workers under 18 years of age are not allowed to work in certain times	Not explicitly stated
Prohibition of night work for pregnant women	Act 76 section 2: Employers are prohibited to appoint pregnant workers for night shifts, with a supporting doctor's note stating that it may endanger the fetus or herself.	Article 39 paragraph (1): Pregnant employees may not work between 22.00–06.00, overtime, or on holidays, except for executive/academic/administrative/financial positions and with consent and not endangering health.
Employer obligations when employing women at night	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Act 76 section 3: Employers must Obligated to provide nutritious food and maintain welfare and security Act 76 section 4: Employers must provide transportation for female workers working during 2.00-05.00 	Act 40: Any work deemed dangerous by the inspector between 12.00 AM and 6.00 AM, a request regarding change of working hours must be made and the company must comply
Maternity Leave	Act 82 section 1: A leave of 1.5 months before and 1.5 months after childbirth, based on the assessment of a doctor or midwife	Article 41: Maximum maternity leave is 90 days per pregnancy, including holidays.
Miscarriage leave	Article 82 section 3: 1,5 months of rest or as certified by doctor/midwife	Not explicitly stated
Request of adjustment due to pregnancy	Not explicitly stated	Article 42: Pregnant employees with a doctor's certificate may request a temporary change of duties. Employers must consider more suitable work.
Protection from termination of employment due to pregnancy	Not explicitly stated	Article 43: Employers may not dismiss female employees due to pregnancy.

Apart from the list of regulations mentioned above a deeper look into the regulations will discuss matters in harassment experienced by women in the workplace. Indonesia itself has a series of regulations in an effort to reduce cases of harassment experienced by women in the workplace. In response to the enactment of the 2022 Sexual Harassment Law, the Indonesian Ministry of Manpower issued Decree No. 88/2023, which offers detailed regulations for the prevention and handling of sexual harassment in the workplace. This regulation, a significant update to the 2011 Ministry of Manpower Circular Letter, introduces stricter expectations for employers, including the obligation to establish an anti-harassment task force and proactively support victims during their recovery. In accordance with the 2022 law, the regulation also states that sexual harassment is defined as any unwanted sexual conduct, requests for sexual activity, or verbal or physical behavior or gestures of a sexual nature that offend, humiliate, or intimidate a person and disrupt the work environment. In Thailand, protection for women in the workplace is also strictly regulated through the Labor Protection Act. Article 16 clearly states that an employer, responsible person, superior, or supervisor who commits

sexual harassment, sexual assault, or abuse against an employee may be subject to sanctions. Under Article 147 of the Labor Protection Act, anyone violating Article 16 will be subject to a fine of up to twenty thousand baht. The Thai Criminal Code provides for sanctions against perpetrators of sexual offenses through a number of applicable provisions. Perpetrators who intimidate, oppress, harass, or cause embarrassment or distress to another person can be fined up to five thousand baht. Meanwhile, those who engage in indecent gestures or act in a public place, or display unwanted sexual behavior in a public space, face up to one month in prison and/or a maximum fine of ten thousand baht. If the act is committed by someone in a position of authority over the victim, such as an employer, the perpetrator remains subject to the same criminal penalties and fines, but their actions are considered a more serious violation from a moral and social perspective. In addition, government officials in Thailand are subject to the provisions of the Labor Protection Act (LPA) and the Civil Service Act B.E. 2551 (2008), which regulates disciplinary action against civil servants found to have committed sexual harassment or sexual assault. These forms of sexual violence or harassment are outlined in the regulations of the Office of the Civil Service Commission (OCSC), specifically Articles 8 and 83 of the Civil Service Act B.E. 2551. Article 10 of the Notification of the State Enterprise Labor Relations Committee on Minimum Standards of Employment Conditions in State Enterprises, which refers to the State Enterprise Labor Relations Act B.E. 2543 (2000), also provides protection for employees in state-owned enterprises, in line with Article 16 of the Labor Protection Act.

The regulations provided by both Indonesia and Thailand are crucial in ensuring protection for women in the workplace. These regulations cover wages, working hours, leave entitlements, and protection for women experiencing discrimination or harassment in the workplace. All of these provisions are designed to be implemented in all areas of employment, both formal and informal, for women working in Indonesia and Thailand. However, the status of victims of discrimination in the workplace in both countries still faces significant challenges. Despite the existence of a series of regulations specifically aimed at protection, victims still do not receive adequate justice from the authorities. Women who are victims of discrimination must continue to fight to ensure they receive the justice they deserve. The lack of protection for female workers in both Thailand and Indonesia demonstrates that existing regulations are insufficient to eradicate the various problems they continue to face in the workplace. Therefore, it is necessary to establish a special institution or organization specifically tasked with protecting female workers from various forms of discrimination they experience in the workplace. Female workers who are victims of discrimination are still not fully protected, despite the existence of articles governing this in each country's regulations. In Thailand, protection for victims should be provided fairly, accompanied by appropriate penalties for perpetrators, given the existence of various regulations that specifically outline the form of such protection. Meanwhile, regulations in Indonesia are still considered less responsive to protecting women in the workplace. A clear example of discrimination against women in the workplace in Indonesia can be seen in the case of Baiq Nuril Maknun in 2018. Baiq, an honorary teacher at SMAN 7 Mataram, was the victim of verbal harassment by the school principal. Although Baiq did not distribute the recording containing the obscene remarks, she was still charged under Article 27 paragraph (1) of Law Number 11 of 2008 concerning Electronic Information and Transactions (ITE Law), as amended by Law Number 19 of 2016. The recording in question was kept by Baiq as documentation of the violence she experienced, but was shared by a colleague. Despite this, Baiq was still prosecuted for distributing content deemed obscene, while neither the harasser nor the coworker who distributed the content was prosecuted.

In its cassation decision, the Supreme Court overturned the acquittal decision from the Mataram District Court and declared Baiq guilty. She was sentenced to six months in prison and fined Rp 500 million. The court held that the elements of content dissemination had been fulfilled and violated moral norms, even though Baiq's intention was to preserve evidence of the violation, not to disseminate indecent content. The Supreme Court's decision, which rejected the Mataram District Court's decision, indicated that Baiq had committed a violation based on the recording evidence and witness testimony that her colleague, Haji Imam Mudawin, had distributed the recording. Regarding the application of the ITE Law, the judge stated that the application complied with Article 27 paragraph (1) in conjunction with Article 45 paragraph (1) of the ITE Law. However, the judge failed to consider the violation of morals and decency as stipulated in Article 86 paragraph (1) of Law No. 13 of 2003 concerning Manpower, which states that every worker/laborer has the right to receive protection and treatment in accordance with human dignity and religious values. The judge also ignored the contents of the recording, which clearly showed an indecent conversation between Baiq and her superior, Haji Muslim. The lack of regulations regarding the protection of women at that time was one of the factors that caused Baiq Nuril's failure to achieve justice. In Thailand, similar cases also highlight the weak protection of women, especially when the perpetrators are in positions of power. One case study involved a domestic worker named Pimpa, who was abused by her employer, a Kuwaiti

ambassador. Pimpa filed a complaint with the Don Muang Police Station in hopes of securing legal protection. However, the case was dropped by the police because the ambassador was protected by diplomatic immunity. The police were unable to even summon her for questioning. The ambassador also exerted political pressure on the Thai government to suppress the case.

The above discussion clearly demonstrates that although Indonesia and Thailand have enacted various regulations to protect women from discrimination and harassment in the workplace, their implementation and effectiveness remain far from ideal. The cases of Baiq Nuril in Indonesia and Pimpa in Thailand demonstrate that when perpetrators are in positions of authority or protected by the system, achieving justice for victims becomes increasingly difficult. Existing regulations fail to fully address the complexities of gender-based violence in the workplace, particularly within the context of power, culture, and institutional weaknesses. Therefore, protecting women workers simply requires legal provisions. A real commitment from the state, law enforcement agencies, and society is needed to ensure that every working woman has the same right to feel safe, respected, and protected. Establishing a dedicated institution focused on protecting women workers, strengthening complaint mechanisms, and providing gender awareness education in the workplace are crucial steps that must be implemented immediately.

REFERENCES

1. ABNR Counsellors at Law. *New Indonesian Guidelines on Workplace Sexual Harassment: Improvements Still Needed*. [2023].
2. Adawiyah, R., et al. *Analysis of E-Commerce Data Breach and Theft*. [2022].
3. Aparicio, S., Urbano, D., & Audretsch, D. *Economic Development through Entrepreneurship*. [2016].
4. Bangkok Post. *Gender Gap Won't Close Without Change*. [2024].
5. Banton, M. *Racial Theories*. [1998].
6. Garner, B. A. (Ed.). *Black's Law Dictionary (9th ed.)*. [2009].
7. Boonyasith, C. *Workplace Discrimination and Harassment: Protecting Employee Rights under Thai Laws*. [2024].
8. Business & Human Rights Resource Centre. *Women's Human Rights & Business in ASEAN*. [n.d.].
9. Cameron, L. *Gender Equality and Development: Indonesia in a Global Context*. [2023].
10. Grown, C. *Gender Equality and Women's Economic Empowerment: The Role of World Bank Group*. [2024].
11. Constitution of the Kingdom of Thailand B.E. 2560 (2017). *Unofficial English Translation*. [2017].
12. Equality and Human Rights Commission. *The Equality Act: Guidance for Small Businesses*. [n.d.].
13. Folbre, N. *The Rise and Decline of Patriarchal Systems*. [2018].
14. Fraenkel, J. R., & Wallen, N. E. *How to Design and Evaluate Research in Education (6th ed.)*. [2006].
15. Hyland, M., et al. *Female-Owned Firms During the COVID-19 Crisis*. [n.d.].
16. Indonesia Business Coalition for Women Empowerment. *Sexual Violence Afflicts Many Workers in Indonesia*. [2023].
17. International Labor Rights Fund, Rights for Working Women Campaign, & Kompipote, U. *Sexual Harassment in the Workplace: A Report from Field Research in Thailand*. [2002].
18. Keliat, V., & Chan, A. *Perlindungan Hukum terhadap Perempuan dan Anak akibat Perkawinan Siri Pasca Bercerai*. [2025].
19. Komnas Perempuan. *CATAHU 2024: Menata Data, Menajamkan Arah*. [2025].
20. Labour Protection Act B.E. 2541 (1998), Thailand. *English Translation*. [1998].
21. Legal Dictionary. *Discrimination in the Workplace*. [n.d.].
22. Mahanakorn Partners Group. *Sexual Harassment in the Workplace*. [2021].
23. Oceanio, V. D. *Maternity Leave and Gender Equality: Comparative Studies of Indonesia, Malaysia, and Thailand*. [n.d.].
24. OECD Development Centre. *Thailand SIGI Country Profile 2023*. [2023].
25. Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights. *Women's Rights Are Human Rights*. [2014].
26. Pakpahan, M. E., Zulkifli, S., & Sunarto, A. *Perlindungan Hukum Pemberian Kredit secara Digitalisasi kepada Debitur*. [2022].
27. Peraturan Menteri PPPA No. 6 Tahun 2023. *Parameter Kesetaraan Gender dalam Peraturan Perundang-undangan*. [2023].
28. Republik Indonesia. *UU No. 13 Tahun 2003 tentang Ketenagakerjaan*. [2003].
29. Republik Indonesia. *UU No. 11 Tahun 2020 tentang Cipta Kerja*. [2020].
30. Republik Indonesia. *UU No. 12 Tahun 2022 tentang Tindak Pidana Kekerasan Seksual*. [2022].

31. Republik Indonesia. *UU No. 6 Tahun 2023 tentang Penetapan Perppu Cipta Kerja menjadi UU*. [2023].
32. Rahardjo, S. *Ilmu Hukum*. [2000].
33. Soekanto, S. *Pengantar Penelitian Hukum*. [1986].
34. State Enterprise Labour Relations Act B.E. 2543 (2000), Thailand. [2000].
35. Sunarto, K. *Pengantar Sosiologi (3rd ed.)*. [2004].
36. Thai Enquirer. *Women in Modern Thailand Still Face Obstacles*. [2022].
37. UN Women. *Thailand Country Profile*. [n.d.].
38. UN Women. *ASEAN Gender Outlook: Launch and Outcome Document*. [2025].
39. UNESCO. *Gender Equality in Higher Education in Southeast Asia*. [2022].
40. Verick, S. *Female Labor Force Participation in Asia: Trends and Constraints*. [2018].
41. Violita, C. W., et al. *Peranan Investasi Asing dalam Percepatan Pertumbuhan Ekonomi di Indonesia*. [2020].
42. Walker, J. *How Can Thailand Improve Workplace Discrimination and Harassment Laws?* [2025].
43. Wikipedia contributors. *Gender Inequality in Thailand*. [n.d.].
44. Wikipedia contributors. *Keadilan*. [n.d.].
45. World Bank. *Women, Business and the Law 2022: Indonesia Snapshot*. [2022].
46. World Bank Group. *Thailand – Women, Business and the Law 2024*. [2024].
47. World Economic Forum. *Global Gender Gap Report 2024*. [2024].
48. Yesenia, S., et al. *The Increase of Divorce Rates in Early Marriage in the Midst of the Pandemic*. [2022].
49. Vara-Horna, A. A., et al. *Direct and Indirect Effects of Workplace Sexual Harassment*. [2023].

Cite this Article: Yesenia, S., Rizal, S., Simanjuntak, I. (2025). Comparison Study between Regulations Implementations in Indonesia and Thailand to Protect Women from Discrimination in the Workplace. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 8(7), pp. 3829-3833. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i7-73>